

QUIZ**LAST NAME: VOLZ****FIRST NAME: TOBIAS****PROGRAM CODE: MMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **Which of the following answers is not a criterion of a good essay, according to EUCLID’s course material on academic paper writing?**
 - An academic essay should answer a specific question.
 - An academic essay should include relevant examples.
 - An academic essay should give a brief overview over a theory.¹**
 - An academic essay should include supporting evidence.

2. **Which of the following statements summarizes “paraphrasing,” according to EUCLID?**
 - Paraphrasing is writing a summary of some else’s text in one’s own words and citing it.²**

¹ EUCLID, “ACA-401 Period 1,” 2015, <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1/>. (accessed on 5 February 2020), 2

² Ibid., 23

- Paraphrasing is changing some of the author's original words to make it one's own and add a citation to the source.
 - Paraphrasing is putting quotation marks around an original part of another writer's document and citing it.
 - Paraphrasing is using the author's original idea without referring to the source.
3. **Which of the following comma rules is, according to EUCLID, incorrect?**
- One can use a comma to bracket phrases, regardless, if the phrases are essential to a sentence's meaning or not.³**
 - One can use a comma to bracket phrases if the phrases are not necessary for the meaning of a sentence.
 - One can use a comma to bracket nonrestrictive phrases.
 - One can use a comma to join two independent clauses.
4. **According to Turabian's manual, which of the following statements about citation is incorrect?**
- Conducting research can be challenging and take a lot of time. Even though some authors get financially compensated for their research, receive prizes, or a promotion at work, in many cases, it is unpaid. However, recognition, pride, and prestige through seeing one's name as a reference in another research is also prestigious for an author's hard work. Citation is an excellent possibility to give credits and recognition for someone else's hard work.

³ EUCLID, "ACA-401 Period 1", 46

- Academics do not only refer to sources they utilize for their projects, but also data which contradicts, or corrects their paper. Therefore, citing helps the reader to connect one's research to other research in a specific area and to understand one's document better.
 - Correct academic citation is a big challenge, proofs trustworthiness, and will always be rewarded. Researcher often invest a lot of time to internalize different citation rules and styles, such as Turabian, WHO, or Blue Book Style. Readers will see the hard work and award this effort in every case through showing recognition, such as through citing the research, financially, or positive feedback.**⁴
 - Citation does not only enable the reader to check one's research reliability but is also often used to extend the research paper, for example, in a different direction.
5. **Turabian said that conducting research includes collecting data. However, researchers can use data differently. How do researchers, according to Turabian, often think about their aim?**
- Most researchers want the reader to learn more than just a collection of facts. Researchers look for precise data to support an answer to a particular question.**⁵
 - Researchers are aware of the fact that they have to put a lot of efforts in their work to convince the reader. The aim is mostly to show the reader that their research is the best in the field.
 - Researcher want to challenge themselves. The answers researchers try to find are usually complex, challenging, and time-consuming. It can be challenging for students to learn relevant skills required for excellent

⁴ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students & Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. William, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff., 8th Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86-87

⁵ Ibid., 15-16

- research. Therefore, many researchers want to show the reader what they learned, how well they write, and what they have to say.
- Researchers want to become a source of inspiration themselves. By answering questions, giving answers, and creating data, researchers want to stimulate the reader mentally and to empower the reader to do something similar.
6. **Which of the following quotation is not mentioned by Sebranek, Kemper, and Meyer (1999) as a recommendation to enhance writing habits?**
- “Write every day, preferably at a set time.”
 - “Write as well as you can... by your own standards.”
 - “Become a student of writing.”
 - “Write as much as you can.”⁶**
7. **Which of the following sentences has correct punctuation, according to the European Commission?**
- The research document which has been edited, can now be submitted.
 - Sam cleaned, Jack mowed the lawn and Sue watched TV.⁷**
 - The board of the company dealing with management decisions agreed on hiring the new director but the proposed candidate for the project manager position was rejected.
 - The German Ambassador prefers ”a high-level meeting with the country’s elite” to an informal get-together with his neighbors.

⁶ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000. A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning*. (Massachusetts: Great Source Education Group, a division of Houghton Mifflin Company., 1999)., 14

⁷ European Commission, “English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission.”, 7th Edition, 2011, /dl/xitMjHAGfJ. (accessed 5 February, 2020), 14-22

8. **Academic writing requires a very formal writing style. Which of the following sentences would be inappropriate in an academic paper, according to EUCLID?**

- The director stated: “The transportation industry has changed. Nowadays, many people rather take the train to save the environment.”
- He wrote: “The interviewer highlighted that this was his first interview with a high-level politician.”
- She read: “However, the participant mentioned that researcher in the last century didn’t have the tools and knowledge to conduct quantitative interviews.”⁸**
- The researcher concluded: “I found the author’s lecture very beneficial and would highly recommend her book to anyone working in this field.”

9. **Which of the following sentences applied correct UK English punctuation?**

- She read: “George resisted, “I am a free man!” and ran away.”
- Dear Mr Smith: Thank you for being so helpful.
- He said: ‘The girl threw the frisbee’.⁹**
- They asked: “Why are we here?”

10. **According to EUCLID, what is relevant in a paper?**

- It is relevant to provide detailed background information to give the reader a complete picture of a theory.

⁸ EUCLID, “ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1.”, 39

⁹ Ibid., 54-59

- The writer should always focus on correct citation.**¹⁰
- If writers are students, they need to mention their field of study.
- The use of the superlative is recommended in academic papers to emphasize a point.

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¹⁰ EUCLID, "ACA-401 Coursepack Period 4", <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/YIJXVLgPv0/> (accessed on 5 February 2020), 8-10